

Field Work Resources

May 2026

It's the start of the 2026 field season. For many of us that means outdoor activities, long days, remote locations and lots of logistics to sort through. This month's newsletter focuses on fieldwork, specifically, two topics may have slipped through the cracks of pre-season planning, field discussions and checklists: **1) field safety for at-risk individuals, 2) menstruation in the field.**

We also share links to funding opportunities aimed at helping students meet accessibility needs, which includes during field work.

1. Safe Fieldwork for At-Risk Researchers: What We All Need to Know

(Illustration by Callie Rodgers Chappell)

Not everyone walks into the field facing the same risks. Researchers from underrepresented backgrounds— including women, those from non-majority racial or ethnic groups, LGBTQ+ individuals, people with disabilities, and religious minorities—face increased risk of hostility, harassment, and physical danger in fieldwork settings.

- At-risk researchers carry the mental weight of anticipating potential harassment long before they reach a field site. That cognitive burden erodes their capacity to do the work they came to do.
- Compounding this, supervisors who don't share their students' identities are often simply unaware that these risks exist, leaving a gap in preparation and support
- Risk is fluid! Someone who blends in at their home institution or academic environment can become a visible minority or a visible outsider the moment they step into the field.

What this means for each of us:

Researchers should carry institutional credentials at all times, establish a daily check-in contact, document known risks at sites with a history of incidents and speak up when something feels unsafe.

For supervisors, field researchers, coordinators, and team leads:

- Build a written field risk management plan before the season starts.
- Self-educate on risks your team members may face—without asking them to relive trauma to teach you.
- When a researcher raises a concern, believe them and adjust accordingly.
- At the Departmental or research group level, there is real value in having field safety and harassment training as a standard requirement, ensuring researchers have official institutional affiliation letters when doing fieldwork and regularly collecting anonymous feedback on whether field sites feel safe for everyone.

(Adapted from [Demery and Pipkin \(2021\)](#))

2. Menstruation in the field: Considerations and Resources

(Illustration by Current Conservation)

Menstruation is a normal part of life for many researchers, yet it rarely comes up in pre-field planning. In remote settings this gap creates real problems. Limited sanitation, no privacy, schedules that ignore pain or fatigue can create a team culture where people don't feel comfortable raising these needs.

For supervisors, field researchers, coordinators, and team leads:

- Include sanitation stops in the itinerary from the start and keep them there; avoid impromptu group votes that can override one person's unspoken need
- Keep an emergency supply of menstrual products accessible from a designated person.
- Brief the whole team on facilities available each day, ideally with three comfort breaks (mid-morning, lunch, mid-afternoon).
- Allow workload flexibility on high-discomfort days.
- Normalize the conversation! Bring it up in pre-departure briefings like any other logistics item.

Practical product options:

- **Menstrual cups:** wearable up to 12 hours, reusable, low waste; practical for long field days.
- **Period underwear:** good all-day backup, needs washing facilities.
- **Disposables:** carry wet wipes, hand sanitizer and ziplock bags for used products.
- **Period delay medication:** prescribed by a doctor; can delay menstruation by days to weeks; worth discussing with a healthcare provider several months before fieldwork.
- **For pain management:** replicate what works at home: ibuprofen or adhesive heat patches are field-friendly options.

(Adapted from: [EDI in the field: Menstruation Considerations](#) by Emily Swerdfager and [Menstruation in the field](#) by Bethan Davies and Becky McCerery)

Resource Tips of the Month: Funding to meet accessibility needs

Field safety is not optional. Same goes for ensuring accessibility and disability requirements are identified and planned for well ahead of the season.

Personal safety gear, training courses, and accessibility equipment can be expensive, cost shouldn't be the reason someone heads into the field unprepared.

- Start talking to your supervisor. Whether it's a piece of gear, specific training or equipment related to a disability or accessibility need, it is a reasonable conversation to have before the season starts.
- There is also support available on campus worth knowing about:
 - [University of Alberta Bursaries and Emergency Funding](#)
 - [University of Alberta Accessibility and Accommodations](#)

The DBS EDI committee is honoured to have received the **FoS EDI award** at the 2026 celebration of excellence!

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Have ideas for future newsletters or want to get in touch? Email us at dbsemi@ualberta.ca or share your feedback [here](#).